

Statistical distances in 35 indigenous varieties of rice, U.P., India.

lowest for Budhiabanko and Sugarimohar, followed by Sukhdas and Churamani.

An examination of the percent contribution of each character to divergence showed grain yield as the major con-

tributor (77.8%) followed by days to maturity and days to heading. Plant height and spikelets per panicle contributed equally (1.8%) toward D^2 . Test weight contributed the least (0.5%) to D^2 . ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Rice tungro virus resistance in medium-duration prerelease cultivars

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Cultivars of all crops performing significantly better in yield and quality than

the existing cultivars are tested in adaptive trials in farmers' fields before release. During 1980, medium-duration cultivars TNAU 15776-3, AD6380, and DPI 591 were evaluated with three standard ones — Ponni, IR20, and M. Boothy — at 12 sites in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu.

Since its appearance in Thanjavur in

1978, tungro has been the primary disease in rice cultivation. The medium-duration cultivars raised in adaptive trials in the district were evaluated for their relative resistance to rice tungro virus. With the 12 sites as replications, the data on the rice tungro virus were statistically scrutinized (see table).

Mean incidence of rice tungro virus (RTV) at Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Culture	Parentage	RTV (%) ^a	
		AV	TV
DPI591	IR1712/IR1330	4.4	12.1
AD6380	IR8/Co25	5.1	13.1
M. Boothy	Tg65/ME80	12.5	20.7
Ponni	TG65/ME80	13.8	21.8
IR20	IR262/TKM6	65.4	54.0
TNAU15776-3	ASD5/IR20	89.1	70.7
C.D. = (P = 0.05)			6.3

^aAV = actual percentage of RTV worked out. TV = transformed value (angular value) for the actual percentage.

DPI 591 and AD6380 recorded a very low tungro incidence of about 5%. That indicated their high field resistance to the disease. If released as new varieties, the two cultivars can be best utilized in the rice tungro problem areas. ■

Resistance to bacterial blight

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Rice cultivars were screened for resistance to bacterial blight disease. The plants were raised in pots containing wetland soil and in the field spaced 20 × 10 cm. Fertilizers were applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. The plants were inoculated at three stages: seedling (20 days), tillering (50 days), and boot-leaf. The disease severity was scored on a scale of 0-9. Many cultivars were rated susceptible; a few were moderately resistant.

Interestingly, ASD5 was resistant, comparable with TKM5 until tillering. IR22 and IR26 were moderately susceptible and ASD5 was resistant in the tillering stage. But ASD5 became infected in the panicle-emergence stage. Progeny of ASD5 — TNAU7124 and TNAU 15776 — also scored resistant until tillering and were moderately susceptible in the boot-leaf stage. The con-

Reaction of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial blight disease.

Variety or culture	Disease severity scale ^a					
	Seedling		Tillering		Boot-leaf	
	Pots	Field	Pots	Field	Pots	Field
BJ1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sigadis	0	0	0	0	1	0
TKM6	1	0	1	0	1	1
ASD5	1	0	1	1	5	5
IR22	1	1	5	3	5	5
IR26	3	1	5	5	5	5
Pankaj	1	1	3	1	3	3
TN1	5	5	7	7	7	7
TNAU7124 (ASD5/IR22)	1	1	1	1	5	3
TNAU15776 (IR20/ASD5)	1	1	1	1	5	3
ASDIS (IR22/IR26)	3	3	7	1	7	7

^a0 = not affected, 9 = highly susceptible.

tribution of resistance by IR22 and IR20 in those two cultivars appears insufficient. ASD15 (IR22/IR26) is also susceptible (see table).

ASD5 has potential resistance until

the tillering stage to the bacterium strain that causes severe damage to most of the improved rice varieties that are known to be bacterial blight resistant. ■

Root knot nematode—*Fusarium* complex in rice under dryland conditions in Brazil

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A root disease complex is affecting rice in the savannas (cerrados) of the states of Goias, Mato Grosso do Sul, and Mato Grosso where dryland rice is extensively grown.

The symptoms on the aboveground parts were retarded growth, reduced tillering, and pale yellow leaves. The symptoms were evident about 25 days after planting and the difference in height between diseased and healthy plants increased with time.

The affected farmers' fields showed light yellow patches of plants exhibiting retarded growth, and some nutritional disorder was generally suspected. But when the plants were pulled out, a black discoloration was seen at the underground basal node where adventitious roots are initiated. This discoloration extended along the mesocotyl, but seldom to the adventitious roots. Examination of transverse sections of the root at the underground basal node of the culm showed discoloration of vascular tissues. Death of the affected plants was,

however, uncommon.

Isolating more than 50 diseased plant samples from different fields yielded 2 distinct species of *Fusarium*. Inoculation tests using diverse isolates showed that one of the two species was highly

pathogenic. The identification of the pathogenic species is under way.

The incidence of root knot nematode caused by *Meloidogyne javanica* was observed after 75 days of crop growth in the experimental plots at the National Center of Rice and Beans, as well as in some of the farmers' fields affected with *Fusarium*.

Preliminary evaluation of the field incidence in 12 dryland rice cultivars, each grown in plots of 900 m², showed significant differences in the percentage of plants affected by root infection caused by *Fusarium*, root knot nematode, and both root knot and *Fusarium* (see table). While the plants showing galls and egg masses on the roots incited by *M. javanica* had no symptom on the aerial parts, the plants affected with *Fusarium* infection singly or in combination with root knot nematode were retarded in growth and had few tillers.

The root disease complex was commonly found in the second and third year of successive rice cultivations in savannas or in fields where rice is grown in rotation with pasture. ■

Incidence of *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Fusarium* sp. in 12 rice cultivars under upland conditions in Brazil.

Cultivar	Total number of plants	Infected plants ^a (%)	
		<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	<i>M. javanica</i>
Early maturing			
Pratao Precoce (standard)	518	93.71	35.99
Dourado Precoce	402	81.79**	3.49**
IAC 25	303	66.78**	27.31
Medium duration			
IAC 47 (standard)	365	69.86	43.12
Pratao	434	56.32**	40.38
IAC 1246	385	53.18**	38.46
Iguape Redondo	428	46.91**	44.49
Fernandes	294	43.21**	38.67
Amarelao	270	37.23**	62.20**
IAC 5544	312	32.27**	48.27
IRAT 13	261	31.62**	55.77
Bico Ganga	305	29.72**	33.66

^aData presented include combined infection of *Fusarium* and *Meloidogyne*. Mean percentages marked with asterisks are significantly different from the standard checks as judged by t-test at the 1% level of probability.

Evaluation of resistance to rice blast in observation plots of Bagua

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Materials selected from rice blast infection beds were tested for resistance to leaf blast (seedling stage) and neck blast (adult stage) in 20-m² observation plots in fields where the incidence of blast was high. Additional information was taken